

Article

Spatiotemporal Dynamics of Riparian Land-Cover Change and Impervious-Cover Expansion in a Rapidly Urbanising Himalayan Capital City

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Abstract

Urbanisation and impervious-cover expansion are reshaping riparian landscapes, particularly in mountain cities where steep terrain concentrates development along valley floors. This study examined spatiotemporal land-cover change within the regulated riparian corridors of Thimphu City, Bhutan, over a 25-year period from 1997 to 2022 using Landsat imagery, Random Forest classification and Google Earth Engine. Results show substantial transformation of riparian land cover, with impervious cover increasing from 26.14% to 32.63%, equivalent to an overall increase of 24.83%, while agriculture/barren/low-vegetation declined from 30.59% to 26.01%, equivalent to an overall decrease of 14.98%. A modest increase in detectable vegetation cover was also observed, although this should be interpreted cautiously because the study measured land-cover extent rather than vegetation condition, floristic composition or ecological quality. Classification performance was robust, with overall accuracies ranging from 89.9% to 94.5%, exceeding the commonly accepted 85% benchmark, although uncertainty remains in narrow riparian corridors due to Landsat's 30 m spatial resolution. Mann–Kendall analysis provided supplementary evidence of monotonic land-cover trends, but the limited number of temporal observations means these results should be interpreted as indicative, rather than definitive. Spatial analysis revealed uneven transformation, with the southern valley recording the greatest increase in impervious cover. These findings demonstrate sustained development pressure within legally regulated riparian buffers and highlight the need for routine spatial monitoring, place-specific buffer management and stronger integration of riparian protection into urban planning. The study provides a quantitative baseline for assessing future riparian land-cover change and supporting more resilient land governance in rapidly urbanising Himalayan mountain cities.

Keywords: impervious cover; riparian areas; land-cover change; spatiotemporal analysis; mountain urbanisation; land governance

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1. Introduction

Urbanisation is widely recognised as a dominant driver of landscape transformation across the globe, fundamentally altering the structure and function of terrestrial ecosystems [1]. This is especially pronounced in rapidly expanding cities, where urban growth is often unregulated and unaccompanied by ecologically informed planning [2]. A key manifestation of urbanisation is the widespread replacement of vegetated or permeable land covers with impervious cover such as buildings, roads, sidewalks, and other

infrastructure [3–6]. These changes not only modify the landscape’s physical appearance, but also disrupt hydrological and ecological processes, increasing surface runoff and altering local microclimates and biodiversity patterns [7–9].

Among the most affected landscapes by urbanisation are riparian zones: ecotones at the interface of terrestrial and aquatic systems [10]. These areas, comprising riverbanks, floodplains, and associated vegetation [11], provide vital ecosystem services such as flood mitigation, nutrient retention, and biodiversity support [12,13]. Due to their flat topography and proximity to water, riparian zones are often targeted for development [14,15], and, in many cities, remaining riparian corridors serve as some of the last urban green spaces [16]. As urban areas expand, these sensitive ecosystems become increasingly fragmented and degraded, which threatens their ecological integrity [17,18].

Beyond ecological impacts, riparian transformation also represents a significant land governance challenge. In rapidly urbanising mountain cities, development pressure is commonly concentrated within narrow valley floors and river corridors, where relatively flat land is available for settlement expansion [19,20]. Under such conditions, conflicts frequently emerge between urban development objectives and environmental protection regulations, particularly where institutional enforcement capacity, monitoring systems, and long-term planning mechanisms are limited [21,22]. Although riparian buffer regulations are often formally established, implementation may be inconsistent, due to competing demands for housing, infrastructure, and commercial development [21,23]. This creates a practical governance problem: legally protected riparian buffers may remain vulnerable where development demand is high, developable land is scarce, and spatial monitoring is insufficient. Understanding how urban growth interacts with regulated riparian spaces is therefore essential not only from an ecological perspective, but also for providing spatial evidence relevant to planning, regulatory implementation, and land management in rapidly transforming cities [19,24].

Despite extensive research in developed countries, there remains a lack of empirical studies on the impact of urbanisation, particularly the expansion of impervious cover, on riparian zones in developing cities. Existing studies have primarily focused on either general urban expansion patterns or broad-scale ecological impacts, while comparatively few have examined riparian land-cover dynamics at the buffer scale over extended time periods [25–27]. Furthermore, studies integrating remote sensing-based land-cover monitoring with questions of riparian governance, regulatory implementation, and spatial planning remain particularly limited in Himalayan cities [28]. Three specific gaps are therefore evident: limited long-term time-series evidence on riparian land-cover change, limited buffer-scale assessment of impervious-cover expansion within regulated corridors, and limited integration of remote-sensing evidence with land-governance questions in mountain-city contexts. These gaps are especially relevant in the Himalayan region of South Asia, where cities are rapidly expanding. Without timely intervention and reliable baseline data, riparian ecosystems may undergo substantial transformation before their full ecological value is understood or incorporated into planning frameworks. These systems are both climatically and ecologically unique [29], making them particularly vulnerable to mounting urban pressures.

Thimphu, the capital of Bhutan, provides a compelling case study of such urban–riparian interactions. Since the late 1980s [30], the city has witnessed unprecedented population growth and impervious-cover expansion, particularly along the banks of the Wang River. Between 2000 and 2020, impervious cover in Thimphu city expanded more than four times, from 8 km² to 36.5 km² [31], a transformation clearly observable in satellite imagery and on the ground (Figure 1). Much of this expansion has occurred within valley-floor landscapes historically characterised by agriculture, open land and low vegetation,

increasingly converting permeable or low-intensity land covers into impervious surfaces. This trend is likely to continue as rural-to-urban migration intensifies [32] and Thimphu consolidates its role as Bhutan's economic centre [33].

Figure 1. Transition from low-intensity, non-impervious riparian land covers to more impervious cover-dominated landscapes in the Thimphu Valley. (a) Northern Thimphu: views from 1984 (B & F Shaw) and 2022 (Choki Gyeltshen); (b) Southern Thimphu: views from 1974 (Leo Van Der Velden) and 2022 (Leki Dorji); and (c) Central Thimphu: Google Earth satellite views from 2003 and 2022.

Urban development in Thimphu is strongly constrained by mountainous terrain, resulting in a concentration of settlement and infrastructure within narrow valley bottoms and river-adjacent areas [34]. At the same time, Bhutan's Forest and Nature Conservation Rules and Regulations (FNCRR) 2017 mandate riparian buffer protection along rivers and streams [35]. However, increasing development pressure within Thimphu's valley floor raises important questions regarding how effectively regulated buffer zones can be

maintained under rapid urban expansion. These dynamics make Thimphu particularly suitable for examining how topographic constraints, urban growth pressure, and riparian governance interact within a Himalayan riparian system.

Despite the magnitude of these changes, there is limited empirical research assessing how impervious-cover expansion has reshaped the spatial configuration and potential ecological vulnerability of riparian areas in Thimphu. Previous studies in the Himalayan region have rarely provided long-term, spatially explicit analyses of riparian land-cover change using consistent time-series remote sensing approaches [36,37]. In addition, few studies have quantified impervious-cover expansion specifically within regulated riparian buffers or evaluated spatial differences in urban encroachment patterns across different parts of a mountain city [31]. Urban management strategies imported from cities in differing climatic and developmental contexts may be ill-suited to address the unique challenges associated with steep terrain, narrow developable corridors and competing land-use demands, potentially exacerbating local vulnerabilities and hindering effective management [38]. Therefore, a nuanced understanding of land-cover dynamics is critical to inform context-appropriate, adaptive strategies that reconcile urban development with riparian ecosystem conservation.

This study presents a spatiotemporal analysis of land-cover change within the regulated riparian corridors of Thimphu City between 1997 and 2022 using Landsat imagery, Random Forest (RF) classifier and Google Earth Engine (GEE) v1 platform (JavaScript Client API, accessed May 2026). The specific objectives are to (i) quantify long-term land-cover dynamics within Thimphu's regulated riparian areas, including spatial variation across the city; (ii) assess the magnitude and temporal pattern of impervious-cover expansion and associated changes in other land-cover classes; and (iii) establish a spatial baseline to support future riparian monitoring and planning. By linking long-term satellite-based monitoring with formal buffer regulation and mountain-city development pressure, this study provides spatial evidence relevant to riparian land governance in rapidly urbanising Himalayan cities.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Study Site

Thimphu is the capital and largest city in Bhutan (89°38'25.44" E, 27°28'41.16" N) (Figure 2). It is home to over 0.14 million of Bhutan's 0.78 million people, making it the country's largest and most densely populated city [39,40]. The city is surrounded by hills covered with scrub and blue pine forests (*Pinus wallichiana*). The density of impervious cover is highest on the flat terrain of riparian areas and valleys, gradually decreasing as the terrain transitions to gentle slopes and then to steep slopes in the peri-urban areas (Figure 1a,b; Figure 2). The elevations of the area studied ranged from 2190 to 2890 metres above sea level. Thimphu is classified as having a subtropical highland climate (Cfb) according to the Köppen–Geiger climate classification system [41]. This type of climate is typified by clearly defined seasons, with cold and dry winters and warm and wet summers [42]. The mean annual temperature is 14.7 °C, and the annual precipitation is 608.9 mm, with most of this falling in the wet season (the June-to-August average is 371.3 mm) [43].

The Wang River, which originates from the glaciers and snowfields of the Himalayas, flows southward, traversing the entire length of Thimphu City. Five major tributaries join the Wang River along its course through the city: *Dechencholing chhu* (*chuu* means river or stream), *Samteling chhu*, *Chuba chhu*, *Olarong chhu*, and *Ngabirong chhu*, before exiting the city. During the study period, the average wet channel width of the Wang River was 19 metres, with a range between 5.5 and 35 metres, while the tributary stream wet channel

width varied from 2 to 6 metres. The minimum and maximum flow rates of the Wang River are approximately 3.4 and 47.6 cubic metres per second, respectively, with an annual average flow rate of approximately 17.3 cubic metres per second [43].

Figure 2. Maps of Bhutan, Thimphu district and Thimphu City.

Urban development in Thimphu is strongly constrained by mountainous topography, resulting in the concentration of settlement, infrastructure, and commercial activities within narrow valley bottoms and riparian corridors. Consequently, river-adjacent areas represent some of the few relatively flat and developable areas of lands available for urban expansion. Riparian areas in Bhutan are formally regulated under the FNCRR, which mandates protected buffer zones along rivers and streams. However, increasing urbanisation pressure within Thimphu's valley floor has intensified land-use competition between development needs and ecological protection objectives.

Urban growth in Thimphu has been guided primarily by the Thimphu Structure Plan (TSP) 2002–2027, a long-term spatial planning framework prepared to promote environmentally sustainable and culturally responsive urban development. The TSP provides the principal spatial planning framework for Thimphu City and emphasises land-use planning through urban villages, local area plans, land-use precincts, infrastructure provision, environmental enhancement zones, and open-space systems [44]. It also seeks to integrate urban growth with the protection of the natural environment and Bhutanese cultural heritage. Despite these objectives, rapid population growth and increasing development pressure have substantially altered planned land-use patterns, particularly within valley-floor riparian areas. The Strategic Environmental Assessment of the TSP notes that implementation has been affected by weak enforcement, limited institutional and financial capacity, weak ownership of the plan, changes in planning decisions, and deviations from the original planning intent [44]. This makes Thimphu an appropriate case study for examining in-

teractions between urban expansion, riparian transformation, and land governance in a Himalayan mountain-city context.

2.2. Delineation of Riparian Zone

A fixed-width buffer of 30 m was applied consistently to delineate riparian zones along both the Wang River and its tributary streams throughout the study. This width aligns with the recommendation of Holmes and Goebel [45], who suggested a minimum of ~100 feet (~30 m) in areas where the bank slope exceeds 5% and floodplain borders are difficult to identify. It also corresponds with Bhutan’s FNCRR 2017, which requires a 30 m buffer along rivers and streams [35].

The use of a uniform 30 m buffer ensured consistency with the legally regulated riparian corridor and allowed direct comparison of land-cover change across all study years. However, because mountain riparian systems vary with channel width, slope, floodplain form and geomorphology, this fixed-width approach may not fully represent the functional ecological boundary of all riparian areas. Therefore, the results should be interpreted as land-cover changes within the regulated riparian buffer, rather than the full geomorphological riparian system. Because the buffer width is comparable to the 30 m spatial resolution of Landsat imagery, the analysis was designed to detect dominant corridor-scale land-cover patterns, rather than fine-scale encroachment or parcel-level regulatory compliance.

The delineation was carried out using QGIS (version 3.28), and the buffer area obtained was the region of interest for subsequent land-cover classification carried out in GEE.

2.3. Datasets and Land-Cover Classification

2.3.1. Study Period and Rationale

This study analysed land-cover-change dynamics in Thimphu City and its riparian areas over a 25-year period, from 1997 to 2022, at five-year intervals. This temporal window captures the most significant phases of Thimphu’s urban transformation following major government planning initiatives, including the establishment of the National Urban Development Commission after 1985 and the 2002 government decision to expand the city [30].

2.3.2. Satellite Imagery and Preprocessing

Landsat multispectral imagery was used for 1997, 2002, 2007, 2012, 2017 and 2022 (Table 1). Images were accessed and processed in GEE. Because the study spans multiple Landsat missions, sensor-appropriate Landsat imagery was used for each observation year, including Landsat 5 TM, Landsat 7 ETM+ and Landsat 8 OLI. Comparable spectral bands were selected across sensors to maintain temporal consistency in land-cover classification.

Table 1. Details of satellite imagery datasets used in this study.

Year	Satellite/Sensor	Path/Row	Resolution	Image Acquisition Period	GEE Dataset Collection
1997	Landsat 5 TM	138/41	30 m	1 January–31 December 1997	LANDSAT/LT05/C02/T1_L2
2002	Landsat 7 ETM+	138/41	30 m	1 January–31 December 2002	LANDSAT/LE07/C02/T1_L2
2007	Landsat 7 ETM+	138/41	30 m	1 January–31 December 2007	LANDSAT/LE07/C02/T1_L2
2012	Landsat 7 ETM+	138/41	30 m	1 January–31 December 2012	LANDSAT/LE07/C02/T1_L2
2017	Landsat 7 ETM+	138/41	30 m	1 January–31 December 2017	LANDSAT/LE07/C02/T1_L2
2022	Landsat 8 OLI	138/41	30 m	1 January–31 December 2022	LANDSAT/LC08/C02/T1_L2

To ensure strict radiometric consistency across the multi-decadal time-series, all data were sourced from Landsat Collection 2 Tier 1 Level 2 Surface Reflectance (SR) products (<https://www.usgs.gov/landsat-missions/landsat-collection-2-surface-reflectance>

(accessed on 1 May 2026). These data were radiometrically corrected to absolute surface-reflectance values using sensor-specific scaling factors—specifically, applying a multiplication factor of 0.0000275 and an offset of -0.2 to the optical bands.

For each study year, images were filtered to the corresponding annual period from 1 January to 31 December, and clipped to the study boundary. Scene-level cloud contamination was reduced by selecting images with low cloud cover, and pixel-level cloud and cloud-shadow contamination were masked using the QA_PIXEL band and sensor-appropriate bitwise masking procedures in GEE. A median composite was then generated for each year to reduce the influence of residual clouds, atmospheric effects and scene-specific noise.

Vegetation information was strengthened by calculating the Normalised Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) and adding it as an additional predictor variable. Crucially, to preserve the physical integrity of the vegetation index tracking, NDVI was calculated from the radiometrically scaled surface-reflectance data using the appropriate near-infrared and red bands for each Landsat sensor. For Landsat 5 TM and Landsat 7 ETM+, NDVI was calculated using SR_B4 and SR_B3, while for Landsat 8 OLI, NDVI was calculated using SR_B5 and SR_B4. The use of annual median composites and NDVI helped improve spectral separation among impervious areas, vegetation, waterbodies and low-cover land classes.

Although Landsat's 30 m spatial resolution limits fine-scale interpretation in narrow riparian corridors, Landsat provides one of the few consistent multi-decadal datasets suitable for long-term urban land-cover monitoring in Bhutan. Higher-resolution imagery with comparable historical coverage was not consistently available for the entire 1997–2022 study period. Therefore, classification outputs were interpreted at the landscape and riparian-corridor scale, rather than as parcel-level boundaries.

2.3.3. Classification Approach

A supervised classification approach was employed using the RF classifier in GEE. Training samples were extracted from the annual composite images using labelled reference points. The predictor variables included sensor-comparable multispectral bands and NDVI.

Because different Landsat sensors were used across the study period, a standardized set of seven comparable spectral bands representing the visible, near-infrared, and shortwave-infrared regions (Bands 1–5 and 7 for Landsat 5/7; Bands 2–7 for Landsat 8), along with the derived NDVI band, were strictly maintained as the uniform inputs for all classification years. Thermal bands, cirrus bands, and panchromatic bands were not used as predictor variables, to maintain cross-sensor consistency. The RF classifier was selected because of its strong performance in heterogeneous urban landscapes, resistance to overfitting and suitability for handling multi-band satellite data [46,47]. The model was trained using 100 decision trees, with other classifier parameters left at GEE default settings. The trained classifier was then applied to each annual composite to produce land-cover maps for the six study years.

2.3.4. Land-Cover Typology and Sample Collection

Land cover was classified into four primary categories: impervious cover, vegetation, waterbodies, and agriculture/barren/low-vegetation (Table 2). Training and validation samples were derived from high-resolution Google Earth imagery and field observations, where available.

The agriculture/barren/low-vegetation class was retained as a combined category because cultivated land, fallow land, exposed soil and sparse seasonal vegetation showed substantial spectral overlap in 30 m Landsat imagery. Separating these subclasses would likely increase classification uncertainty, particularly in heterogeneous riparian and peri-

urban areas. Moreover, the primary goal of this study is to compare changes in impervious-cover expansion and detectable vegetation cover. Therefore, this class should be interpreted as a broad low-intensity or non-impervious land-cover category, rather than as agricultural land alone.

Table 2. Description of land-cover types in Thimphu City and its riparian areas.

Land-Cover Type	Land-Cover Description	No. of Samples
Impervious cover	Built-up areas and infrastructure, including buildings, roads, pavements and parking areas.	70
Vegetation	Natural and managed vegetation, including forests, shrublands, riparian vegetation and urban green spaces.	109
Waterbodies	Rivers, streams, ponds and other permanent or semi-permanent surface water features.	64
Agriculture/barren/low-vegetation	Cultivated land, fallow land, exposed soil, barren surfaces and sparse or seasonal vegetation.	67

A total of 310 reference sample points were collected across the study area. The samples were randomly divided into approximately 80% for training and 20% for validation, using a random split procedure in GEE. Stable and visually identifiable pixels were prioritised during sample selection to reduce classification ambiguity and improve temporal consistency. However, this approach may reduce sensitivity to highly dynamic transitional pixels, particularly along narrow riverbanks where land cover changed rapidly. This limitation was considered when interpreting land-cover transitions and small class changes.

2.3.5. Accuracy Assessment

Classification accuracy was assessed using the independent validation dataset. Validation samples were classified using the trained RF model, and a confusion matrix was generated for each year. Overall accuracy, user's accuracy, producer's accuracy and the Kappa coefficient were calculated from the confusion matrix.

An overall accuracy of 85% was used as a reference benchmark, in line with recommendations from recent studies that employed Landsat imagery and RF classifiers in complex terrain [48,49].

Because the analysis focused on narrow riparian corridors, particular attention was given to uncertainty associated with mixed pixels and edge effects. At 30 m spatial resolution, riverbank pixels may contain mixtures of vegetation, water, exposed soil and impervious surfaces. This is especially relevant because the riparian buffer width is also 30 m. Therefore, the classified outputs were interpreted as corridor-scale patterns, rather than exact parcel-level boundaries. Visual comparison with high-resolution Google Earth imagery was used to check whether classified maps reasonably represented land-cover patterns across different parts of Thimphu.

2.3.6. Area Estimation and Spatial Comparison

Land-cover area was calculated in GEE using pixel-based area estimation. To eliminate distortions caused by map projections in Thimphu's mountainous terrain, the exact area calculation was executed geodesically. The classified image was combined with the `ee.Image.pixelArea()` function, which dynamically computes the area of every single pixel on the true ellipsoidal surface of the Earth. The area of each land-cover class was summed within the study boundary and riparian buffer, using a grouped spatial reduction. Area values were converted from square metres to square kilometres by dividing the resulting metric sum by 1,000,000.

This approach provides spatial quantification of land-cover change suitable for long-term trend analysis across multiple decades [48]. The resulting area estimates were used to quantify land-cover composition for each study year and to calculate temporal percentage changes in land-cover classes.

Overall change (%) was calculated as

$$\text{Overall change(\%)} = \frac{P_{2022} - P_{1997}}{P_{1997}} \times 100$$

Average five-year change (%) was calculated as

$$\text{Average five - year change(\%)} = \frac{1}{n - 1} \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} \left(\frac{P_{t_{i+1}} - P_{t_i}}{P_{t_i}} \times 100 \right)$$

where P represents the proportional area of a given land-cover class, P_{1997} and P_{2022} represent the class proportions in the first and final study years, respectively, t_i represents each observation year, and $n = 6$, corresponding to 1997, 2002, 2007, 2012, 2017 and 2022. These metrics were used to describe the magnitude and temporal pattern of land-cover change, rather than annualised rates.

To examine spatial variation in land-cover change, Thimphu City and its associated riparian corridors were divided into northern, central and southern sections along the main north–south valley axis. Land-cover areas were calculated separately for each section, using the same classified maps and pixel-area approach. This allowed comparison of spatial differences in impervious-cover expansion and associated land-cover changes across the city.

2.3.7. Land-Cover Transition Analysis

To identify the dominant land-cover conversion pathways, a pixel-based transition matrix was generated for the first and final study years, 1997 and 2022. The classified land-cover maps for 1997 and 2022 were cross-tabulated using a change-detection code calculated as

$$\text{Transition code} = (LC_{1997} \times 10) + LC_{2022}$$

where LC_{1997} and LC_{2022} represent the land-cover class values in 1997 and 2022, respectively.

The frequency of each transition code was calculated using a frequency histogram reducer in GEE. To maintain consistency with the area estimates, transition areas were calculated by combining the transition-code image with `ee.Image.pixelArea()` and summing the area of each transition class within the study boundary and riparian buffer, using a grouped spatial reduction. Area values were converted from square metres to square kilometres. Transition matrices were generated separately for the whole Thimphu City boundary and the regulated riparian buffer.

2.3.8. Statistical Analysis

A Mann–Kendall trend test was conducted to assess monotonic temporal trends in the areal extent of riparian land-cover classes. Kendall’s tau was used to evaluate the direction and strength of trends, and statistical significance was assessed at the 95% confidence level.

3. Results

3.1. Classification Accuracy Assessment

As shown in Table 3, overall classification accuracy exceeded the recommended 85% threshold for all years, with overall accuracy (OA) ranging from 89.9% (2012) to 94.5% (2022) and Kappa coefficients ranging from 0.87 to 0.93. Most land-cover classes

achieved user’s accuracy (UA) and producer’s accuracy (PA) values above 85% throughout the study period. Impervious cover, vegetation and waterbody classes consistently demonstrated strong classification performance.

Table 3. Land-cover classification performance as represented by user’s accuracy (UA), producer’s accuracy (PA), overall accuracy (OA) and Kappa values.

LC Class	Accuracies	1997	2002	2007	2012	2017	2022
Impervious cover	UA%	91.3	96.4	88.1	97.7	97.5	95.3
	PA%	93.3	92.9	94.9	84	95.1	95.3
Vegetation	UA%	94.2	96.6	92.9	83.8	92.5	93.5
	PA%	96.1	90.6	96.3	96.2	89.3	96.6
Waterbodies	UA%	93.1	89.3	92.9	97.1	96.1	91.3
	PA%	100	96.1	94.4	100	96.1	91.3
Agriculture/barren/low-vegetation	UA%	87.5	87.5	87.5	80	86.6	96.6
	PA%	87.8	93.3	82.3	84.2	92.8	87.8
	OA%	94.1	93.1	91.9	89.9	93.5	94.5
	Kappa	0.92	0.90	0.89	0.87	0.91	0.93

Classification performance was comparatively lower in 2007 and 2012, particularly for the agriculture/barren/low-vegetation class (PA = 82.3% in 2007; UA = 80.0% in 2012) and vegetation class in 2012 (UA = 83.8%). These comparatively lower accuracies likely reflect spectral overlap among sparse vegetation, exposed soils and transitional land covers within heterogeneous riparian environments, together with mixed-pixel effects associated with Landsat’s 30 m spatial resolution.

Because the analysis focused on narrow riparian corridors, classification uncertainty associated with edge effects and mixed pixels was expected, especially along tributary channels where riparian widths approached or fell below the spatial resolution of Landsat imagery. However, visual comparison with high-resolution Google Earth imagery indicated that the classified outputs reasonably represented the dominant spatial patterns of urban expansion and riparian land-cover transformation across the study area.

Despite these limitations, the consistently high OA and Kappa values indicate that the classification outputs were sufficiently reliable for analysing long-term land-cover change trajectories at the riparian-corridor scale.

The classified land-cover maps for the first and final study years are shown in Figure 3. Intermediate maps for successive years are not shown because the study area is relatively small and visual differences among five-year classifications were less distinct at the map scale. The 30 m riparian buffer boundary is also not displayed separately, to avoid visual clutter. The full temporal pattern is quantified in Tables 4 and 5.

Table 4. Temporal comparison of land-cover (LC)-class extent from 1997 to 2022 for the entire Thimphu City.

LC Class	1997	2002	2007	2012	2017	2022	Average Five-Year Change (%)	Overall Change (%)
Impervious cover	26.3	28.0	32.1	33.8	35.8	36.5	6.9	38.9
Vegetation	32.0	32.5	33.4	30.8	32.0	30.0	−1.1	−6.1
Waterbodies	4.6	4.7	3.8	5.1	7.2	7.2	11.9	57.4
Agriculture/barren surface/low-vegetation	37.1	34.8	30.7	30.2	25.1	26.2	−6.4	−29.4
Total	100	100	100	100	100	100		

Figure 3. Classified land-cover maps of Thimphu City for 1997 and 2022.

Table 5. Temporal changes in land-cover (LC)-class extent within the riparian areas of Thimphu City from 1997 to 2022.

LC Class	1997	2002	2007	2012	2017	2022	Average Five-Year Change (%)	Overall Change (%)
Impervious cover	26.14	25.00	33.00	30.50	32.80	32.63	5.42	24.83
Vegetation	18.30	20.20	16.80	13.70	15.70	18.90	2.02	3.28
Waterbodies	24.96	25.50	16.00	18.10	21.40	22.46	0.24	−10.02
Agriculture/barren surface/low-vegetation	30.59	29.40	34.20	37.60	30.10	26.01	−2.23	−14.98
Total	100	100	100	100	100	100		

3.2. Land Cover in Thimphu City and Its Riparian Areas

Between 1997 and 2022, Thimphu City underwent substantial land-cover transformation (Table 4). Impervious cover increased from 26.3% in 1997 to 36.5% in 2022, representing an overall increase of 38.9% and an average five-year increase of 6.9%. In contrast, agriculture/barren/low-vegetation declined from 37.1% to 26.2%, corresponding to an overall decrease of 29.4% and an average five-year decline of 6.4%. Vegetation declined moderately from 32.0% to 30.0%, while waterbodies increased from 4.6% to 7.2% over the study period.

Riparian areas also experienced notable land-cover transformation between 1997 and 2022 (Table 5). Impervious cover increased from 26.14% to 32.63%, representing an overall increase of 24.83% and an average five-year increase of 5.42%. Agriculture/barren/low-vegetation declined from 30.59% to 26.01%, corresponding to an overall decrease of 14.98% and an average five-year decline of 2.23%. Waterbodies declined from 24.96% to 22.46%,

while vegetation increased slightly, from 18.30% to 18.90%. These changes indicate that riparian land-cover transformation was mainly characterised by expansion of impervious surfaces and contraction of low-intensity non-impervious land-cover areas, although waterbody and vegetation estimates should be interpreted cautiously because narrow riparian corridors are sensitive to mixed-pixel effects and seasonal variation.

Because the agriculture/barren/low-vegetation category represents a combined low-intensity land-cover class, rather than agricultural land alone, the observed decline may have resulted from a general reduction in non-impervious and sparsely vegetated surfaces associated with urban expansion. Therefore, this change should not be interpreted narrowly as direct agricultural land loss.

The substantial increase in impervious cover within riparian corridors indicates continued urban encroachment into river-adjacent valley-floor land, despite the existence of legally regulated riparian buffer protections under the FNCRR 2017. This pattern reflects increasing land-use competition between urban expansion and ecological protection.

A statistically significant negative trend was observed between impervious cover and agriculture/barren/low-vegetation areas within riparian corridors (Kendall's $\tau = -0.97$, $p = 0.007$), indicating a consistent decline in low-intensity land-cover surfaces concurrent with increasing urban expansion. Given the small sample size ($n = 6$), both Kendall's τ and the p -value appear highly significant. However, despite this statistical significance, the result should be interpreted cautiously, serving as supplementary evidence of trend direction rather than definitive proof of a strong temporal relationship.

Impervious cover showed a moderate positive association with vegetation cover ($\tau = 0.41$), while vegetation exhibited a negative association with agriculture/barren/low-vegetation areas ($\tau = -0.50$); however, these relationships were not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$). Waterbodies did not demonstrate statistically significant associations with the other land-cover classes during the study period.

Since the Mann–Kendall analysis was based on only six temporal observations, the statistical results should be interpreted primarily as indicative of general trend direction, rather than definitive evidence of strong temporal relationships. Consequently, interpretation focused primarily on mapped spatial patterns and land-cover transition trajectories, rather than statistical inference alone.

3.3. Land-Cover Transition Patterns

Pixel-based transition analysis between 1997 and 2022 showed that impervious-cover expansion occurred largely through the conversion of agriculture/barren/low-vegetation areas, both across Thimphu City and within the regulated riparian buffer (Tables 6 and 7). This provides direct evidence of the conversion pathways underlying the proportional changes reported in Tables 4 and 5.

Table 6. Land-cover transition matrix for Thimphu City between 1997 and 2022. Values are in km². Rows represent 1997 land-cover classes and columns represent 2022 land-cover classes.

1997 → 2022	Impervious Cover	Vegetation	Waterbodies	Agriculture/Barren/Low-Vegetation	1997 Total
Impervious cover	4.84	0.48	0.52	1.14	6.98
Vegetation	1.20	5.94	0.67	0.69	8.50
Waterbodies	0.28	0.24	0.61	0.09	1.22
Agriculture/barren/low-vegetation	3.38	1.32	0.12	5.05	9.87
2022 total	9.69	7.98	1.92	6.97	26.56

For the whole city, the largest conversion to impervious cover was from agriculture/barren/low-vegetation land, which accounted for 3.38 km². This represented approximately 69.6% of all newly converted impervious areas from previously non-impervious classes. Vegetation-to-impervious and waterbody-to-impervious transitions were smaller,

accounting for 1.20 km² and 0.28 km², respectively. Persistent impervious cover accounted for 4.84 km², indicating that much of the urban footprint present in 1997 remained impervious in 2022. Overall, 16.44 km², or approximately 61.9% of the analysed city area, remained in the same land-cover class, while 10.12 km², or approximately 38.1%, changed class during the study period.

Table 7. Land-cover transition matrix for riparian areas between 1997 and 2022. Values are in km². Rows represent 1997 land-cover classes and columns represent 2022 land-cover classes.

1997 → 2022	Impervious Cover	Vegetation	Waterbodies	Agriculture/Barren/Low-Vegetation	1997 Total
Impervious cover	0.99	0.14	0.32	0.49	1.94
Vegetation	0.09	0.69	0.17	0.12	1.08
Waterbodies	0.23	0.15	0.84	0.13	1.34
Agriculture/barren/low-vegetation	0.89	0.02	0.07	0.85	1.83
2022 total	2.20	1.00	1.40	1.58	6.19

Within the riparian buffer, the dominant transition pathway was from agriculture/barren/ low-vegetation land to impervious cover, accounting for 0.89 km² between 1997 and 2022. This represented approximately 73.6% of newly converted impervious area from previously non-impervious classes within the riparian corridor. Smaller contributions to new impervious cover came from waterbodies to impervious cover (0.23 km²) and vegetation to impervious cover (0.09 km²). Persistent impervious cover accounted for 0.99 km², while 0.85 km² of agriculture/barren/low-vegetation land remained unchanged.

Overall, 3.37 km², or approximately 54.4% of the riparian buffer, remained in the same land-cover class between 1997 and 2022, while 2.82 km², or approximately 45.6%, changed class. These transition results indicate that riparian urban expansion occurred primarily through the conversion of low-intensity, non-impervious land-cover surfaces into impervious cover.

However, because the agriculture/barren/low-vegetation class combines cultivated land, exposed soil, barren surfaces and sparse vegetation, this transition should not be interpreted narrowly as agricultural land loss alone. Rather, it reflects a broader reduction in low-intensity land-cover surfaces within river-adjacent areas. In the context of Thimphu's narrow valley-floor setting, this pattern suggests increasing pressure on regulated riparian corridors where developable land is limited, and urban expansion is concentrated close to river channels. This transition evidence strengthens the land-governance interpretation of the study by showing that new impervious surfaces were primarily associated with conversion from low-intensity land-cover surfaces within regulated river corridors.

3.4. Spatial Variation in Land-Cover Change Across Thimphu

Land-cover transformation differed substantially among the northern, central and southern regions of Thimphu City and their associated riparian areas (Figure 4).

The southern region experienced the greatest increase in impervious cover (70.2%), indicating that urban expansion was concentrated primarily within the southern valley corridor. In contrast, the central region exhibited the greatest proportional decline in detectable vegetation (−22.5%) and agriculture/barren/low-vegetation areas (−32.5%), relative to the northern and southern regions.

Vegetation trends differed among regions, with vegetation increasing in northern Thimphu (13.3%) but declining in the central and southern regions. Waterbody extent remained unchanged across all three regions during the study period. Because waterbody estimates are sensitive to river width, seasonal flow and mixed pixels, this apparent stability should be interpreted as a broad land-cover pattern, rather than evidence of unchanged hydrological condition.

Figure 4. Spatial comparison of land-cover dynamics across the northern, central, and southern regions of Thimphu City and their associated riparian areas during 25 years of urban expansion (1997–2022).

The pronounced concentration of impervious-cover expansion in southern Thimphu likely reflects the greater availability of relatively flat and developable valley-floor land compared, with the more topographically constrained northern and central sections of the city. These spatial differences are broadly consistent with the direction of planned urban expansion under the Thimphu Structure Plan 2002–2027. However, because this study did not formally analyse planning boundaries, road accessibility, land prices or development permits, these explanations should be interpreted as plausible contextual explanations, rather than directly tested drivers.

The observed spatial variability indicates that urban expansion pressure and riparian transformation are not uniformly distributed across the city, but are instead concentrated in areas with greater development suitability and infrastructure accessibility. This spatial pattern provides the basis for the policy discussion that follows, particularly the need for more targeted monitoring and management in southern riparian corridors.

4. Discussion

This study provides a comprehensive assessment of spatiotemporal land-cover dynamics in Thimphu City, with particular emphasis on riparian areas. The results reveal substantial landscape transformation over the 25-year study period, characterised by a pronounced expansion of impervious cover and a corresponding decline in agriculture/barren/low-vegetation areas. Within the regulated riparian buffer, impervious cover increased from 26.14% in 1997 to 32.63% in 2022, while agriculture/barren/low-vegetation land declined from 30.59% to 26.01%. These changes were especially evident within riparian corridors, highlighting increasing development pressure within ecologically sensitive valley-floor environments. However, because this study measured land-cover extent, rather than hydrological processes or ecological condition, broader environmental implications should be interpreted as likely consequences, rather than direct outcomes of the analysis.

4.1. Classification Performance

The classification of land cover using the RF algorithm in GEE yielded consistently high accuracy across all time points, with OA exceeding the recommended 85% threshold and Kappa coefficients remaining above 0.87 [50]. These results indicate robust model performance [51], supported by the use of cloud-masked annual composite imagery, NDVI-assisted classification, and carefully selected training samples [52,53]. The stability of these accuracy metrics across multiple years strengthens confidence in the reliability of the long-term land-cover trends identified in this study, particularly the sustained expansion of impervious cover within riparian areas.

Some variability in class-specific accuracies (<85%) was observed, notably for waterbodies and agriculture/barren/low-vegetation classes. This may be attributed to seasonal spectral variability, terrain-shadow effects, and mixed pixels within heterogeneous riparian environments [54,55]. Given the transitional nature of riparian landscapes, spectral overlap between adjacent classes can influence classification outcomes when using medium-resolution imagery [56,57]. This limitation is particularly relevant for the combined agriculture/barren/low-vegetation class, where exposed soil, sparse vegetation, fallow land and fragmented agricultural surfaces often exhibit similar spectral responses in 30 m Landsat imagery. Consequently, observed declines within this class should be interpreted cautiously as reductions in low-intensity and non-impervious surfaces, rather than as direct measures of agricultural land loss alone.

The 30 m spatial resolution of Landsat imagery corresponds closely to the 30 m riparian buffer applied in this study, which may introduce edge effects and mixed-pixel uncertainty along narrow corridors [54,56]. This scale issue is particularly important because, in some locations, the regulated riparian corridor may be represented by only one Landsat pixel across the buffer width. Although this spatial alignment may result in minor over- or underestimation of specific classes, the consistent temporal trends observed across all years indicate that these limitations do not materially affect interpretation of the broader patterns of riparian transformation [58]. Accordingly, the findings should be interpreted primarily at the corridor and landscape scale, rather than as parcel-level representations of land-cover change. Future studies could incorporate higher-resolution imagery, object-based classification, or fuzzy accuracy-assessment approaches, to further reduce uncertainty within narrow riparian zones [54,56].

4.2. Drivers of Land-Cover Change

The riparian areas of Thimphu City underwent pronounced land-cover transformation between 1997 and 2022, characterised by a substantial increase in impervious cover, together with marked declines in agriculture/barren/low-vegetation areas. These changes are closely associated with rapid demographic and economic growth, particularly following the intensification of national development initiatives after 2002. Between 2005 and 2017, Thimphu's population increased by 44.7% [39], reflecting urbanisation trajectories comparable to those reported in other rapidly expanding cities [59–61]. However, because this study did not formally model demographic, economic, road-network or land-price drivers, these factors should be interpreted as plausible contextual explanations, rather than directly tested causal mechanisms.

The transition analysis strengthens this interpretation by showing that agriculture/barren/low-vegetation cover was the dominant source of new impervious cover between 1997 and 2022. Across Thimphu City, 3.38 km² of this class was converted to impervious cover. This indicates that urban expansion was not simply an increase in built-up area in already urbanised locations, but involved the conversion of previously low-intensity, non-impervious surfaces. In the riparian context, this is particularly important because such surfaces may provide infiltration capacity, open space and transitional land between built infrastructure and river channels [62,63]. However, because the class aggregates cultivated land, exposed soil, barren surfaces and sparse vegetation, the transition should not be interpreted narrowly, as agricultural loss alone. Rather, it indicates a broader reduction in low-intensity land-cover surfaces within river-adjacent areas [63].

Urban expansion within southern Thimphu likely reflects a combination of relatively accessible terrain, lower topographic constraints, and planned urban-growth direction under the Thimphu Structure Plan 2002–2027. The TSP provides the principal spatial planning framework for Thimphu Thromde and emphasises land-use planning through

urban villages, local area plans, land-use precincts, infrastructure provision, environmental enhancement zones and open-space systems. It also seeks to integrate urban growth with protection of the natural environment and Bhutanese cultural heritage [44]. Although this study did not directly evaluate planning effectiveness or enforcement capacity, the observed increase in impervious cover within legally regulated riparian corridors suggests that development pressure has progressively intensified within river-adjacent areas [62], despite the existence of formal buffer protections under the FNCRR 2017. This interpretation is consistent with the Strategic Environmental Assessment of the TSP, which reported implementation challenges including weak enforcement, limited institutional and financial capacity, weak ownership of the plan, changes in planning decisions, and deviations from the original planning intent [44]. Similar tensions between ecological regulation and development demand have been documented in rapidly urbanising mountain and riverine cities, where institutional enforcement capacity struggles to keep pace with urban growth [64].

Notably, impervious-cover expansion was accompanied by a modest increase in detectable vegetation cover within riparian areas, from 18.30% in 1997 to 18.90% in 2022. In many high-income cities, similar trends are associated with formal greening programmes [61,65,66]; however, no large-scale coordinated urban-greening initiatives have been systematically documented in Thimphu. Because this study assessed land-cover extent, rather than vegetation condition or ecological quality, the observed increase in vegetation should not be interpreted directly as evidence of ecological improvement. The increase may instead reflect localised landscaping, natural regeneration, mixed-pixel effects, or riverbank planting activities involving species such as weeping willow for stabilisation and flood mitigation purposes [67]. This interpretation should remain cautious, because the present study did not include species-level mapping, floristic surveys, or vegetation-condition assessment.

With impervious cover increasing to 32.63% of riparian areas by 2022, hydrological processes may be affected through increased runoff, reduced infiltration, and diminished natural flood-buffering capacity [68]. In the Himalayan context, characterised by steep catchments and intense monsoonal precipitation, these changes may heighten downstream flood risk and vulnerability [69,70]. However, because runoff, infiltration and flood response were not directly measured in this study, these should be presented as literature-supported implications, rather than direct empirical findings. Collectively, these findings underscore the importance of integrating spatial monitoring of riparian land cover into urban planning frameworks to support more resilient and ecologically informed development in Thimphu.

4.3. Contribution to Understanding Urbanisation in Thimphu and Policy Implications

This study provides one of the first long-term spatial assessments of land-cover transformation within Thimphu's riparian corridors over a 25-year period. By quantifying the magnitude and rate of impervious-cover expansion within regulated buffer areas, the study moves beyond general urban-growth assessment, and provides spatial evidence of how river corridors have transformed under rapid urbanisation pressure.

The identification of southern Thimphu as a hotspot of impervious-cover expansion further refines understanding of intra-urban spatial dynamics and highlights the role of valley-floor accessibility in shaping urban growth patterns. Impervious-cover expansion is widely recognised as a major driver of hydrological alteration, increased surface runoff, and ecological fragmentation, in urban catchments [63,71]. Although these environmental processes were not directly measured in this study, the observed spatial concentration of impervious expansion within riparian corridors suggests increasing pressure on ecologically sensitive urban landscapes.

Importantly, the findings establish a quantitative baseline against which future land-cover monitoring, restoration efforts and planning interventions can be evaluated. The divergence between Bhutan's legally mandated 30 m riparian buffer under the FNCRR (2017) and the observed increase in impervious surfaces within these zones provides empirical evidence of implementation challenges. Such mismatches between regulatory intent and land development outcomes are commonly observed in rapidly urbanising environments where development demand, limited flat terrain and institutional enforcement pressures occur simultaneously [64,72].

The implications for urban governance in Thimphu are, therefore, substantial. Integrating routine land-cover monitoring into municipal planning processes, particularly within ecologically sensitive riparian corridors, would align with broader calls for spatially informed and evidence-based urban planning [32,64]. Given that the most pronounced impervious-cover expansion occurred within southern riparian corridors, future planning efforts could prioritise these areas for stricter development control, targeted riverbank restoration, and improved monitoring of buffer-zone encroachment. Differentiated management approaches for major river corridors and smaller tributaries may also be necessary, given the varying degree of topographic confinement and development intensity observed across the city.

More broadly, embedding geospatial monitoring platforms such as GEE within municipal workflows could strengthen data-driven governance and improve transparency in land management decision-making. Cloud-based geospatial tools have demonstrated considerable potential for supporting adaptive planning and urban environmental monitoring in rapidly changing cities [73]. By integrating spatial evidence into planning and regulatory frameworks, Thimphu may be better positioned to reconcile continued urban growth with long-term riparian protection and ecological resilience [74]. These recommendations are directly linked to the observed spatial pattern of change, particularly the concentration of impervious expansion in the southern valley, rather than being general planning recommendations alone.

4.4. Implications for Himalayan Urban Riparian Systems

Although centred on Thimphu, these findings have broader relevance for rapidly urbanising Himalayan cities. Mountain settlements are commonly constrained to narrow valley floors, due to steep surrounding terrain, resulting in concentration of infrastructure and settlement along river corridors and increasing pressure on riparian systems [69,75]. The substantial expansion of impervious cover documented in Thimphu reflects a broader structural pattern characteristic of mountain urbanisation processes.

In steep catchments exposed to intense monsoonal rainfall, increasing impervious cover may alter hydrological regimes by increasing surface runoff and peak discharge while reducing infiltration capacity [7,68]. Under projected climate change scenarios, these risks may intensify further [69]. Riparian corridors also support important ecological functions, including biodiversity maintenance, sediment retention, and microclimate regulation [12,62]. While this study did not directly assess ecological functioning or hydrological response, the observed concentration of impervious-cover expansion within riparian corridors highlights the potential vulnerability of these systems under continued urban growth.

The spatial monitoring framework applied in this study provides a transferable approach for assessing riparian land-cover transformation and supporting climate-resilient urban planning in Himalayan mountain cities experiencing similar topographic and developmental constraints. However, this transferability applies mainly to the monitoring

approach and governance framing, rather than implying that all Himalayan cities will follow the same land-cover trajectory observed in Thimphu.

4.5. Study Limitations and Future Research

While this study provides robust evidence of riparian land-cover transformation in Thimphu, several limitations should be acknowledged. First, reliance on Landsat imagery with 30 m spatial resolution introduces potential mixed-pixel uncertainty, particularly within narrow and heterogeneous riparian corridors, where impervious surfaces, vegetation and exposed land occur in close proximity [56,58]. Such spatial complexity may reduce class separability and influence classification precision. This limitation is especially important because the regulated riparian buffer used in this study is also 30 m wide, meaning that in some locations the analysed corridor may correspond to only one Landsat pixel across the buffer width. Therefore, the results should be interpreted as corridor-scale land-cover patterns, rather than fine-scale evidence of parcel-level encroachment or exact regulatory compliance.

Second, the application of a fixed-width 30 m buffer, although aligned with national regulatory standards, may not fully represent the dynamic ecological and geomorphological extent of riparian systems. Floodplain processes, channel migration and topographic variability may extend beyond administratively defined boundaries, meaning that some functional riparian areas may be under-represented [76]. Because sensitivity analysis using alternative buffer widths was beyond the scope of the present study, future research should evaluate how varying buffer widths influence estimates of impervious-cover expansion and riparian transformation. In particular, comparison of 15 m, 30 m and 50 m buffers would help determine whether the main patterns reported here are robust to alternative riparian delineations.

Third, the analysis focused on land-cover extent, rather than ecological condition or hydrological performance. Consequently, changes in vegetation quality, habitat integrity, runoff dynamics and species composition were not directly assessed, limiting interpretation regarding ecosystem functioning and resilience [77,78].

Fourth, the combined agriculture/barren/low-vegetation class limits interpretation of land-use transitions. Although this category improved classification stability under 30 m Landsat resolution, it prevents separation of cultivated land loss, exposed surface conversion, and sparse-vegetation change. Future studies using higher-resolution imagery should separate these subclasses where possible, to improve land-resource management interpretation.

Finally, the Mann–Kendall trend analysis was based on only six temporal observations, and therefore provides limited statistical power. The statistical analysis was used primarily as a supplementary indicator of trend direction, while interpretation relied principally on mapped spatial patterns and land-cover transition trajectories.

Future research could address these limitations by incorporating higher-resolution and multi-sensor imagery, object-based or sub-pixel classification approaches, hydrological modelling, ecological condition assessments, and longitudinal vegetation monitoring. Such integrative approaches would strengthen understanding of functional riparian change and improve the evidence base for resilient urban-riparian planning in Himalayan mountain cities.

5. Conclusions

This study provides a long-term spatial assessment of riparian land-cover transformation in Thimphu City, showing that regulated river corridors have come under increasing development pressure during the past 25 years. Between 1997 and 2022, impervious cover

within riparian areas increased from 26.14% to 32.63%, while agriculture/barren/low-vegetation declined from 30.59% to 26.01%. These changes indicate a gradual shift from low-intensity, non-impervious land-cover surfaces towards more urbanised riparian corridors.

The findings highlight an important governance challenge for Himalayan mountain cities, where steep terrain limits developable land and urban growth is often concentrated along valley floors and river corridors. In such settings, uniform buffer regulations may be insufficient unless supported by routine geospatial monitoring, stronger development control, and spatially targeted management. The southern valley, identified as the main hotspot of riparian transformation, should therefore be prioritised for stricter monitoring, buffer enforcement, and riverbank restoration.

The study also shows the value of long-term satellite-based monitoring for establishing a quantitative baseline of riparian change. However, the findings should be interpreted within the limitations of 30 m Landsat imagery, the use of a fixed-width buffer, and a broad land-cover classification scheme. The study directly demonstrates land-cover transformation and impervious surface expansion; broader implications for hydrology, ecological condition and climate resilience should be treated as likely consequences requiring further empirical testing. Future research should incorporate higher-resolution imagery, alternative buffer-width assessments, hydrological modelling, and ecological condition surveys, to better evaluate the functional consequences of riparian transformation and support more resilient urban-riparian governance.

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